

IMPROVEMENT OF INDEPENDENT CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF STUDENTS BASED ON COMPETENCE APPROACH

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Abstract. *The basic knowledge, skills and abilities of students are formed only in the process of independent learning, the ability to work independently develops, they become interested in creative work. Therefore, one of the main tasks of a higher educational institution is planning, organizing students' self-study and creating all the necessary conditions for this, along with teaching students in the classroom, teaching them to study more diligently, indicating ways to gain knowledge, issuing directions for self-study.*

Keywords: *independent work, knowledge, skills, formation, development, form, method, personnel, tool.*

According to the requirements of the present time, the educational process does not consist only of imparting knowledge to students, developing their thinking ability, and forming educational skills for using the acquired knowledge. Perhaps, it consists in teaching them the forms, methods and means of finding independent knowledge.

A student can master knowledge deeply only if he is engaged independently and works tirelessly on himself. Students' basic knowledge, skills and competences are formed only in the process of independent education, the ability to work independently develops and interest in creative work appears in them. Therefore, it is necessary to plan, organize and create all the necessary conditions for students' independent study, teach them to study more, and show them ways to learn. , issuing a ticket for independent education is one of the main tasks of a higher education institution. A student's independent work is a systematic activity aimed at mastering a certain part of the knowledge, skills and qualifications specified in the curriculum of a particular subject by the student based on the advice and recommendations of the teacher of the subject and outside the auditorium. Filling students' independent knowledge, extracting what is needed from the flow of information and forming the skills of data processing and analysis is one of the main directions of the quality personnel training process.

Types of independent education include:

- independent mastery of some topics with the help of educational literature;
- preparation of a report on a given topic;
- preparing for practical trainings and seminars;
- preparing for laboratory work;
- performing course work;
- application of theoretical knowledge in practice;
- drawing conclusions and preparing a scientific article based on analytical data on a topic or a certain chapter;
- participation in conferences with lectures;
- preparation of graduation thesis;
- preparing a master's thesis;
- performing homework assignments in subjects;

- preparation of slides and presentations on topics.
- Depending on the characteristics of the taught subject, other forms can be used to organize students' independent work.

The content, essence, form and size of students' independent work, as well as sources, are indicated in the working curricula of the taught subjects.

- In accordance with the time allocated in the curriculum for student independent work, organizational forms of independent work, assignment options are developed and approved by the teaching and method council of the faculty.

-Instructions and recommendations are developed for students in each subject to perform independent work, and they are delivered to students in the first session of the subject as a handout.

The main tasks of independent education include:

- Deepening and expansion of knowledge;
- Formation of interest in creative activity;
- Acquisition of educational methods;
- Development of understanding and thinking ability;
- It includes formation of skills of making independent conclusions.

To effectively organize independent education of students:

- Systematic approach to organization of all forms of students' independent work;
- Coordination and integration of all stages (types) of students' independent work;
- Establish strict control over the quality of independent work of students;
- It is desirable to create and improve a mechanism for organizing and controlling students' independent work.

The procedure for controlling the student's independent work:

- Monitoring of students' independent work is carried out on the basis of the counseling schedule established in each department and approved by the head of the department.

- Consultation hours for students' independent work are recorded in journals established for independent education.

- The supervision of students' independent work is carried out directly by the professor-teacher who conducts training sessions on the subject.

- The independent work of students is evaluated with rating points (in relation to the hour of independent study allocated to the subject) and the result is included in the general rating of the student in the subject.

Tasks of a science teacher in the implementation of independent education:

- Collecting materials related to independent study for the student in accordance with the independent work program, including:

- Control over the implementation of independent education by the student based on the established plan;

- Giving assignments on getting acquainted with textbooks, training manuals, scientific pamphlets, scientific articles;

- Recommending basic literature, information and archival materials and other sources on the topic;

- Conducting consultations based on the schedule with students whose independent work he supervises;

- Regularly providing information about the results of independent education at department meetings;

- Evaluation of independent work results.

The procedure for evaluating the student's independent work

- The criteria for evaluating students' independent work are developed by the relevant departments and approved by the academic council of the faculty.

- The criteria for evaluating independent works are distributed to students together with educational and methodological materials by the professor-teacher of each subject before the beginning of the semester of the academic year.

- Mastering of students' independent work in the field of science is regularly discussed in student groups, at department meetings, and at least 2 times per academic year at the Scientific Council of the faculty.

- Students' independent work is highlighted in the rating window of each department.

- Students' independent work is recorded by the subject teacher in each department and stored during the academic year.

- The independent work of highly rated students in a higher educational institution is encouraged materially and morally.

- Independent works of highly rated students are published on the Web pages of the faculties.

The procedure for organizing independent work and the tasks of the scientific supervisor:

- topics of independent education are given;

- information about the deadline and submission form;

- recommendations of knowledge, skills and qualifications to be acquired by subject

- given in the form;

- literature on the subject is recommended;

- the student is helped in making a plan of the subject;

- constant controls are carried out regarding the implementation of independent work and plans and

- recommendations are given;

- tasks given in the specified period are viewed;

- a test or question-and-answer session will be conducted on the assignment;

- the solutions of practical assignments are shown and checked using similar examples;

- independent work is evaluated based on the established evaluation criteria.

Tasks of the student in organizing independent work:

- In the process of independent work, the student must do the following:

- choose the subject of the work based on the requirements of the department;

- timely completion of assignments based on the plan drawn up by the scientific supervisor perform;

- to submit the account of independent work to the department in time according to the established procedure

REFERENCES

1. Azizkhodjayeva N.N. Pedagogical technology and pedagogical skills. Study guide.-T.; 2013 year.
2. Yoldoshev J.G. A modern lesson. Qualification improvement; problems, research, solutions. XTXQTMOM.-T. named after A. Avloni; 2017 year.
3. Management of students' independent work: method. allowance / under general. edited by I.P. Shepherd, T.G. Argunova. - M.: "UzR DPI" magazine library, 2010.
4. J.E. Usarov, L.G. Babkhodjaeva, G.N. Sharipova, N.J. Eshnaev. Pedagogical competence./Study manual. - Chirchik, "Farzay polygraph". 2021.
5. PEDAGOGICAL FUNDAMENTALS OF MIXED EDUCATION Khalmatova Dilobod Alimzhanovna attachment=12285 2023 – year
6. Khimmataliyev, D. O., Abdijalilova, S. A., Elmurzaeva, N. K., Turaev, M. F., Allayorova, S. B., & Janbayeva, M. S. (2022). Formation Of A Cluster System In The Sphere Of Education In Uzbekistan: Problems And Prospects. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*, 5634-5638.
7. Oblakulovna, Ernazarova Gulnora. "Application Of The Acmeological Approach To Improve The Efficiency Of The Professional Educational Process." *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results* (2023): 2551-2555.
8. Mukhamedov, G. I., Usarov, J. E., Khimmataliev, D. O., Khodjamkulov, U. N., Ernazarova, G. O., & Rasulov, A. N. (2023). Pedagogical Training the Pedagogical and Psychological Foundations of the Innovation Cluster. *Telematique*, 22(01), 29-31.
9. Rakhmanova, M., and M. Meylieva. "Socio-Psychological Features of the Formation of a System of Attitudes to Career Choice in Adolescents." *Indiana Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences* 2.12 (2021): 4-7.
10. Musurmanova, A., Ismailova, Z., Fayzullaev, R., Rakhmonova, M., & Sharifbaeva, H. (2022). Echnologies For The Development Of Technical Competence Of Students On The Basis Of Innovative And Integrated Approaches. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(3), 1631-1637.
11. Mirzaahmadovna M. S. LEARNING OBJECTIVES OF DUAL HIGHER EDUCATION STUDY //Horizon: Journal of Humanity and Artificial Intelligence. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 4. – C. 192-195.
12. Omonovich K. D., Mirzaahmadovna M. S. The Relevance of the Dual Learning Model for Our Country //Telematique. – 2023. – T. 22. – №. 01. – C. 265–274-265–274.
13. Djanbaeva, M. S., & Allayorova, S. B. (2021). AMALIYOTCHI PSIXOLOG SHAXS VA MUTAXASSIS SIFATIDA. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(Special Issue 1), 390-394.
14. Qorayev, S. B., & Allayorova, S. B. (2021). Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini pirls xalqaro baholash dasturi tizimiga tayyorlash jarayonini takomillashtirish masalalari. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(2), 443-448.
15. Mirzotillovayevna, Radjabova Zuhra, and S. R. Mirzayeva. "Psychological factors of adolescence and teacher cooperation in choosing a profession." *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal* 11.5 (2021): 834-842.
16. Mirzotillaevna, Radbajabova Zuhra. "Intelligence as a psychological problem." *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research* 11.10 (2022): 79-82.

17. Musurmonov, R., Eshmanova, N., Satbarov, A., & Elmurzaeva, N. (2021). Innovative Activity In Education-The Requirement Of The Period. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 8(02), 2021.
18. Barakaevich, Qoraev Samaridin, and Sotbarov Atabek Asilbek Ogli. "Requirements for Preparing Vocational Education Teachers in the Innovation Cluster of Higher Education." *JournalNX*: 952-955.
19. Khimmataliev, D. O., Elmurzayeva, N. K., Sharakhmatova, A. K., Sotbarov, A. A., Khalmatova, D. A., & Jamoldinova, S. N. (2022). Development Of The Pedagogical (Educational) Cluster In The Regional Educational Space. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*, 5629-5633.
20. Alimjanovna, Khalmatova Dilobad. "The role and significance of volunteers in the process of formation of ecological culture." *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal* 12.4 (2022): 108-111.
21. Khalmatova, D. A. (2021). Formation of ecological culture in students in the process of extracurricular activities on the example of grades (9-11). In *Актуальные Вопросы Современной Науки И Образования* (pp. 201-203).